

Elastic Buckling of Slender Steel Plates with Perforations

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ABSTRACT

Slender steel plates are employed in many structural forms, and perforations can be added to reduce material consumption with little compromise to elastic buckling capacity. This may increase the structural efficiency of steel sections composed from slender plates. However, there exists little research into the elastic buckling capacity of such plates with many perforations, and how the capacity varies with their location, number, and relative dimensions. It is common to undertake finite element analysis to solve this problem, however the solution accuracy and optimisation are at the compromise of computational efficiency. By considering Rayleigh’s energy method, this paper proposes a mathematical formulation to obtain the elastic buckling capacity of a slender plate with many perforations. Comparisons are made to finite element results, and alternative formulations. The predictions of the proposed method and an existing method are found to give accurate predictions for the elastic buckling capacity, except for plates with perforations of a large aspect ratio, or plates with one row of particularly tall perforations.

Keywords: Buckling, Perforations, Energy method

1 INTRODUCTION TO PLATE BUCKLING THEORY

Perforations equally spaced in a grid-like arrangement in a plate are considered as a ‘regular array’. An ‘irregular array’ of perforations describes a random distribution of differently sized holes, or patterned arrangement that is not regular. Depending on various parameters (such as hole size, location, number), local buckling of a perforated plate may evolve as one of four possible manifestations (*Fig. 1*).

Fig. 1. Local buckling manifestations of perforated plates (a) Whole Plate Buckling (b) Lateral Perforation Buckling (c) Unstiffened Strip Buckling (d) Euler Strip Buckling

Timoshenko (1) derived an expression for the internal bending strain energy of an unperforated plate with given the material properties (plate bending stiffness D and Poisson’s coefficient ν), in terms of the displacement function $w_0(x, y)$ over the plate’s surface area S :

$$U_0 = \left(\frac{D}{2}\right) \int_S \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 - 2(1 - \nu) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial y^2} - \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 \right) dS \quad (1)$$

A rectangular plate with simply supported boundary conditions on all four sides is a lower bound approximation to the web of a cross section. Navier (2) determined an expression for the displacement function of a simply supported plate as a double Fourier series of sinusoidal terms, with amplitudes denoted a_{mn} . If small deflection theory is considered where axial effects are neglected, the surface of a buckled plate can be approximated by this function:

$$w_0(x, y) = \sum_{m=1,3,5}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1,3,5}^{\infty} a_{mn} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} \quad (2)$$

Where a and b denote the length and width of the plate respectively. According to elastica theory, the shortening of an edge under uniform load can be expressed in terms of this out of plane displacement. Accordingly, the external work done to buckle a plate (W_0) is determined:

$$W_0 = \frac{1}{2} \int_S N_x \left(\frac{\partial w_0(x, y)}{\partial x} \right)^2 dS \quad (3)$$

For a simply supported plate, the boundary conditions are known, and the governing differential plate equation can be solved. The critical state is obtained when all amplitude factors a_{mn} (Eq.(2)) are equal to zero, except one (3). The same result is obtained when internal bending strain energy, Eq.(1), and external work, Eq.(3), are equated. The final expression for the buckling capacity N_x is dependant on the plate's geometry (a, b, t), material properties (D, ν), and the number of longitudinal halfwaves (m). This expression is classically given in terms of the plate buckling coefficient (k):

$$N_x = \frac{\pi^2}{b^2} \left(\frac{Et^3}{12(1-\nu^2)} \right) \left(\frac{mb}{a} + \frac{a}{bm} \right)^2 = \frac{\pi^2 D}{b^2} \left(\frac{mb}{a} + \frac{a}{bm} \right)^2 = k \frac{\pi^2 D}{b^2} \quad (4)$$

If defined only by the ratio b/t , a perforated plate may be defined as 'slender' yet undergo elasto-plastic failure. The slenderness depends additionally on the number, shape, size, location and arrangement of perforations (4, 5).

2 LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Several authors carried out computational studies on a range of perforated plates subjected to buckling using the finite element (FE) method (5-10). Each presents their results graphically but provides no expression for the critical elastic buckling capacity of a perforated plate based on the parameters they each assess.

Scheperboer, et al. (4) investigate the buckling of square plates with an irregular array of staggered circular perforations, and propose the elastic buckling capacity as a quadratic function of only the hole area and unperforated plate capacity. Noteworthy, the authors conclude that for the same total perforation area, a plate with more perforations is of lesser capacity. Therefore they only consider the parametric models with the greatest number of perforations investigated to determine the coefficients of this equation by the least square error method (4).

In (11), Kathage et al. present design charts and formulae for the critical buckling capacity of a plate with different arrays of circular perforations subject to pure compression and shear, whereas Shanmugam, et al. (12) propose design formulae for the ultimate capacity of thin plates with a single concentric square or circular perforation subject to different boundary and loading conditions; and Guo & Yao (13, 14) derive closed-form expressions for local buckling according to the size of a single concentric rectangular or circular perforation.

As a small change to any given parameter can greatly influence the perforated plate elastic buckling capacity, a theoretically-derived prediction may have a greater domain of applicability. Several authors empirically modify Generalised Beam Theory (GBT), Finite Strip Method (FSM) or Direct Strength Method (DSM) equations, accounting for perforations with 'effective width' or 'reduced thickness' concepts (14-17). Many design specifications are based on the former method (18-20). Among them, Moen & Schafer (21) theoretically derive closed-form expressions to determine the critical elastic buckling of simply-supported plates with one or multiple perforations. Their work is the primary contribution to the development of DSM to members with holes, and the expressions are similar to those presented by Guo & Yao (13, 14).

A minority of authors evaluate the minimum potential energy of a buckling perforated plate to determine its elastic capacity which involve approximating the displacement function as a sum of functions satisfying kinematic boundary conditions, based on the Lagrange-Dirichlet theorem (22).

Authors are conflicting as to the correct application of the approach to perforated plates. For example, Djelosevic, et al. (23) account for the ‘highly nonuniform’ force redistribution within a plate with a single concentric hole in the calculation of the external work, whereas Gracia & Rammerstorfer (24) demonstrate mathematically that such force inhomogeneity does not directly affect the external work calculation. The authors determine this external work according to *Eq. (3)*, where S represents the net surface (24). Conversely Smith & Moen (25) conservatively consider S to represent the gross surface (i.e. an unperforated plate).

Only Gracia & Rammerstorfer (24) and Smith & Moen (25) present methods applicable to a plate with multiple perforations, and represent the displacement function in terms of ‘amplitude factors’ determined with a Rayleigh-Ritz assessment. The method by Gracia & Rammerstorfer (24) is semi-analytical, reliant on FE analysis to determine a multivariable polynomial approximating the critical modeshape, whereas Smith & Moen (25) present a simpler equation in terms of perforation modification factors, accommodating for the size of the perforation relative to the size of buckled deformations. This solution is developed for the webs of thin-walled members with a regular array of rectangular perforations.

The objectives of this research are to answer the following questions:

- Can existing methods be used outside of the domain within which they were established to accurately determine the critical elastic buckling capacity of perforated plates?
- Can a new solution based on the energy method give a better prediction for the critical elastic buckling capacity of perforated plates for the entire domain investigated?

3 CALIBRATION OF FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

To determine the nature of the relationship between the critical elastic buckling capacity of a perforated simply supported thin plate and the parameters discussed, performance is investigated with the finite element (FE) method. This is determined with the ABAQUS linear perturbation procedure (26), which solves the eigenvalue problem of the constitutive and geometric stiffness matrices.

The material is steel with a Young’s Modulus of 203.4 GPa, and a Poisson’s ratio of 0.3. It is assumed to have isotropic properties and obey the stress-strain relationships for isotropic materials. The perforated plate buckles in the elastic regime, with slenderness determined in accordance with (4, 5). The following limit ensures the plate is slender for all variables investigated in terms of the plate width (b) and thickness (t):

$$\min\left(\frac{b}{t}\right) = 100 \tag{5}$$

As the plate thickness is very small in comparison to the plate dimensions, the problem is adequately described by Kirchhoff shell theory, and thin shell quadratic elements with reduced integration (S8R5) are chosen. A structured mesh is used to negate transverse shear locking and allow for easier data management and thus faster convergence.

It has been shown that a plate with a central circular perforation of diameter equal to the width of a square perforation is of greater capacity (13, 27). This is supported in an assessment on uniaxially compressed square plates undertaken by Narayanan & Chow (28) and holds for eccentric perforations. Yu & Davis (27) attribute this to the difference in stress concentration, opposed to the difference in area of the two perforation shapes. Therefore, this research evaluates plates with an array of rectangular and square perforations, and assumes that the latter is a conservative representation of a plate with circular perforations. All perforations are oriented with their major and minor dimensions parallel to the axes of the global co-ordinate plane, which allows for rectangular FE elements everywhere. A limit is placed on the aspect ratio of elements in the mesh to further ensure accurate convergence, according to an investigation by Moen (29):

$$\min\left(\frac{a_e}{b_e}\right) = 1, \max\left(\frac{a_e}{b_e}\right) = 1.5 \tag{6}$$

Where a_e and b_e represent the length and width of the finite element respectively.

Simply supported boundary conditions are represented as shown in Fig. 2. This is similar to the conditions applied by Sweedan & El-Sawy (6) who examine a symmetrical distribution of circular perforations arranged along the length. Compressive uniform edge loading is simulated by consistent nodal loads, as considered by Moen & Schafer (21).

Fig. 2. Simply supported boundary conditions and nodal loading simulated in ABAQUS

Fig. 3. Regular variables examined

ABAQUS input files are generated with a custom-built python script where these meshing, loading and boundary conditions are prescribed to the model. The limit on the maximum element size is chosen by validating the model to a study conducted by Moen & Schafer (21), who examined 32 FE models of plates with rectangular holes with a corner radius. Despite the holes in this study being sharp-cornered, the results accurately follow the same trend. The element size limit is defined as:

$$\max\left(\frac{b_e}{b}\right) = 0.02 \quad (7)$$

4 PARAMETRIC ASSESSMNET

Regular and irregular perforation arrangements are examined. Rectangular holes may perforate a rectangular area defined by L_{xo} and L_{yo} , which may be located eccentrically about the plate centroid (Fig. 3). The closest distance of this region to the transverse and longitudinal edge is S_{xo} and S_{yo} respectively. Within this region, a regular arrangement of perforations is defined by rows and columns and the number of perforations in each are n_r and n_c respectively. The perforation spacing and size in each direction is also defined in Fig. 3. The domain of these variables is summarised in Table 1 and Table 2 for regular and irregular perforations respectively.

Table 1. Domain of variables examined – Regular arrangement of perforations

	a/b	b/t	n_r	n_c	S_{xo}/a	S_{yo}/b	L_{xo}/a	L_{yo}/b	s_x/a	s_y/b	l_x/a	l_y/b
Minimum	1.0	100	1.0	2.0	0.040	0.040	0.10	0.10	0.006	0.025	0.005	0.02
Maximum	4.0	-	5.0	30.0	0.40	0.40	0.90	0.90	0.70	0.80	0.33	0.80

Table 2. Domain of variables examined – Irregular arrangement of perforations

	a/b	b/t	l_x/a	l_y/b
Minimum	1.0	100	0.009	0.02
Maximum	4.0	-	0.30	0.30

A total of 486 parametric models with regularly spaced perforations have been generated such that the variables are randomly selected from the domain using the python ‘randrange’ function (30). The elastic buckling capacity determined in ABAQUS (N_F) is compared to the prediction given by Scheperboer (4) Fig. 4(a) and Smith & Moen (25) Fig. 4(b) (N_S and N_M respectively). The ratio of the FE result to that predicted by either author for the perforated plate elastic buckling capacity is given on the y-axis. The perforation ratio is the ratio of the total hole area to the gross plate region.

Note that each prediction is applied outside of its established domain. Scheperboer (4) examines staggered circular perforations in a square plate, and Smith & Moen (25) examine a regular array of rectangular perforations symmetric about the mid-length and mid-width of the plate.

Fig. 4. Accuracy of the prediction by Scheperboer, et al (4) (a) and Smith & Moen (25) (b) in comparison to FE results for a regular array of perforations

Fig. 5. Examples of examined plates with a regular arrangement of perforations

For one row of perforations ($n_r = 1$), the prediction by both authors is conservative on average; with a mean of 1.11 and standard deviation of 0.195 compared to a mean of 1.20 and standard deviation of 0.222, the prediction given by Smith & Moen (25) should be used in this case. This standard deviation is a magnitude greater than the standard deviation for models with more than one row of perforations ($n_r > 1$). It can be seen in Fig. 5 that a large proportion of plates with one row of perforations do not exhibit whole plate buckling. The capacity of models G, H and J is underpredicted; these models exhibit lateral perforation buckling and an increased elastic buckling capacity. Model M (Fig. 5) gains a halfwave in comparison to the unperforated plate buckling modeshape, and exhibits an increased elastic buckling capacity (i.e., ‘wavelength stiffening’ (21)). The capacity of Model I (Fig. 5) is overpredicted, and less than the elastic buckling capacity of an equivalent unperforated plate, it clearly exhibits unstiffened strip buckling, not whole plate buckling.

Models with more than one row of perforations exhibit a smaller regression from the prediction derived by Scheperboer, et al. (4). The mean for the 393 models with more than one row of regular perforations is unconservative for both predictions and reduces in accuracy as the number of rows increases. The accuracy reduces at a greater rate for the prediction found by Smith & Moen (25) than for Scheperboer, et al. (4) and this is particularly obvious for models with a large perforation ratio, Fig. 4, Fig. 5. For all 486 models the mean (μ) and standard deviations (σ) are 1.01 and 0.148 for Scheperboer, et al. (4), and 0.962 and 0.129 for Smith & Moen (25) respectively.

The prediction given by Smith & Moen (25) cannot be applied to plates with an irregular array of perforations and only the prediction by Scheperboer, et al. (4) is examined. For such an arrangement, there is no regular spacing or distinguishable rows or columns. Staggered holes and a geometric pattern of holes are included in this definition, in addition to perforations occupying random location within the plate (Fig. 7). The domain of variables is summarised in Table 2.

Fig. 6. Accuracy of the prediction by Schepherboer, et al (4) in comparison to FE results for an irregular array of perforations

Fig. 7. Examples of examined plates with an irregular arrangement of perforations

The accuracy of the prediction determined by Schepherboer, et al (4) for all 320 models with irregular perforations is reduced to that found for a regular arrangement of perforations ($\mu=0.944$, $\sigma=0.0647$). A relationship between elastic buckling capacity and perforation ratio is even less obvious. For example, C, D and E (Fig. 7), and separately K and L (Fig. 7), have the same perforation ratio (and so the same predicted capacity according to Schepherboer, et al. (4)) but exhibit a range of capacities. Models A and E (Fig. 7) are most well-predicted, despite the prediction by Schepherboer, et al. (4) being established in the domain of square plates.

5 MODIFIED ENERGY PREDICTION

Consider a plate subject to uniform compression N_x per unit width along the short edge. When a hole is present, its length along $A'A'$ can no longer provide resistance and the force at this location must be redistributed into the section adjacent to the hole (Fig. 8). This force F_x is an unknown function of y , i.e. $f(y)$, which may be different above and below the hole ($f_1(y)$, $f_2(y)$, Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. The force distribution within an unperforated plate (left) and a perforated plate (right). A length $B'B'$ along the adjacent surface above the hole will displace by a function $w(x, y)$ (grey, right). The unperforated plate function $w_0(x, y)$ is assumed (red, right).

Let the sections above and below the hole be termed the ‘adjacent surfaces’. It is assumed that the force F_x per unit width of plate is constant along the length of the hole $B'B'$ (Fig. 8). The length $B'B'$ displaces by some unknown function $w(x, y)$. It is hypothesised that the modeshape $w_0(x, y)$ of the

unperforated plate is an approximate representation of this unknown function (Eq. (2), Fig. 8). The additional moment in the longitudinal direction $M_{x,F}$ is given in terms of this additional force and unperforated plate displacement function $w_0(x, y)$:

$$M_{x,F} = F_x w_0(x, y) \quad (8)$$

When perforations are arranged in an array, the adjacent surface can be narrow and unsupported along its length. It is assumed that the curvature is uncoupled (beam-like) hence the additional force F_x per unit width is related only to the curvature in the x-direction (κ_x). It follows that the additional energy along the length $B'B'$ (Fig. 8) is given by:

$$U_F = \frac{1}{2} \int_{x_1}^{x_2} M_{x,F} \kappa_{x,0} dx \quad (9)$$

$$U_F = \frac{1}{2} \int_{x_1}^{x_2} (F_x w_0(x, y)) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial x^2} \right) dx$$

Therefore, for the case of a single perforation, the total additional internal strain energy can be expressed as (with x_1, x_2, y_1 and y_2 shown in Fig. 9):

$$U_F = \frac{1}{2} \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \left\{ \int_0^{y_1} (f_1(y)(w_0(x, y)) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial x^2} \right) dy \right\} + \left\{ \int_{y_2}^b (f_2(y)(w_0(x, y)) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial x^2} \right) dy \right\} dx \quad (10)$$

When an array of n perforations is considered, the superposition of the individual i^{th} hole is considered, such that:

$$U_F = \sum_{i=1}^n U_{F,i} \quad (11)$$

$$U_{U_{F,i}} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{x_{i,1}}^{x_{i,2}} \left\{ \int_0^{y_{i,1}} (f_{i,1}(y)(w_0(x, y)) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial x^2} \right) dy \right\} + \left\{ \int_{y_{i,2}}^b (f_{i,2}(y)(w_0(x, y)) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial x^2} \right) dy \right\} dx$$

Considering horizontal equilibrium for each of the i holes, the force function $f(y)$ can be expressed in terms of the applied load function $g(y)$ which is uniform (N_x for the width b). The redistribution of forces adjacent to a perforation is highly nonuniform (23). However, for this research, the critical elastic buckling capacity is evaluated considering a uniform redistribution function and we may assert that a function more representative of the true force-field will be of greater accuracy.

Therefore, we can express the redistributed force as $F_{x,i}$ for the remaining width above and below the i^{th} hole:

$$\int_0^b g(y) dy = N_x = \left\{ \int_0^{y_{i,1}} g(y) dy + \int_{y_{i,2}}^b g(y) dy \right\} + \left\{ \int_0^{y_{i,1}} f_{i,1}(y) dy + \int_{y_{i,2}}^b f_{i,2}(y) dy \right\}$$

$$N_x(y_{i,2} - y_{i,1}) = \int_0^{y_{i,1}} F_{x,i} dy + \int_{y_{i,2}}^b F_{x,i} dy$$

$$F_{x,i} = \frac{N_x(y_{i,2} - y_{i,1})}{b - (y_{i,2} - y_{i,1})} \quad (12)$$

The additional strain energy is a function of the applied force, i.e. $U_F = f(N_x)$. When considering superposition, it is noted that the adjacent surface may not exist, i.e., the adjacent surface of the i^{th} hole may contain another hole (Fig. 9). However, in comparison to the total strain energy, this difference may be considered negligible.

There is strain energy lost at the perforations:

$$U_p = \left(\frac{D}{2} \right) \int_{x_{i,1}}^{x_{i,2}} \int_{y_{i,1}}^{y_{i,2}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 - 2(1 - \nu) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial y^2} - \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_0(x, y)}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 \right) dx dy \quad (13)$$

With U_0 considered for the unperforated plate surface (Eq. (1)), the total internal strain energy of the perforated plate is therefore:

$$U = U_0 + U_F - U_p \quad (14)$$

Fig. 9. Nomenclature of perforation co-ordinates (left) and approximate uniform force function $F_{x,i}$ shown in red for each of the i holes (right)

Rayleigh's quotient is solved, where the external work is conservatively given as established by Smith & Moen (25), and the critical elastic buckling force N_x is determined:

$$N_x = \frac{U_0 - U_p}{\frac{1}{2} \int_S \left(\frac{\partial w_0(x,y)}{\partial x} \right)^2 dS - \frac{U_F}{N_x}} \quad (15)$$

By considering the gross external work, a displacement function that is unchanged to that of the unperforated plate, and by simplifying the shape of the force redistribution function $f(y)$, the elastic buckling capacity of a perforated plate is determined as a 'modified' energy prediction (MEP) as mathematically it is not a 'true' minimum energy potential.

6 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The elastic buckling capacity determined in ABAQUS (N_F) for all 486 regularly and 320 irregularly perforated parametric models is compared to the predictions given by Scheperboer (4) and the MEP (N_S and N_X respectively, Fig. 10). The ratio of the FE-found result to that predicted for the perforated plate elastic buckling capacity is given on the y-axis.

Fig. 10. Accuracy of the prediction by Scheperboer, et al (4) (a) and by the modified energy prediction (b) in comparison to ABAQUS results for all 806 parametric models.

The predictions are of similar accuracies for all models with means of 0.981 and 0.985 for the prediction given by Scheperboer, et al. (4) and the MEP respectively; there is no relationship between the accuracy of either prediction and the aspect ratio of the plate, or the perforation ratio when this exceeds approximately 0.01. Both predictions are highly accurate for very small perforation ratios, and where there is very little difference in the perforated plate buckling modeshape to that of the unperforated plate (for example, models A-F, Fig. 5). This is expected for the MEP, where the modeshape is considered unchanged (Eq. (2)).

The capacity of models C, D and F (Fig. 7) are very accurately predicted with the MEP, with accuracy ratios of 1.001, 1.002 and 0.999 respectively, compared to 0.974, 0.978 and 0.974 found with the

prediction by Scheperboer, et al (4). When the average centroid of all perforations is approximately equal to the location of the antinode, and whole plate buckling manifests, the MEP may enable a more accurate prediction than that determined by Scheperboer, et al (4).

Both predictions are particularly unconservative for plates with holes of a large aspect ratio, where the elastic buckling capacity of the perforated plate is almost half of the unperforated plate (for example, models I, L, N and R, *Fig. 5*, and L, *Fig. 7*). Both predictions are overconservative for plates with one row of particularly tall perforations (for example, models G, H and J, *Fig. 5*), where the elastic buckling capacity of the perforated plate is almost 50% greater than the unperforated plate. At both these extremes, the modeshape greatly deviates from whole plate buckling. However, the underprediction of capacity in the latter examples is less extreme for MEP than it is with (4). Overall, the MEP exhibits less variation in accuracy with a smaller standard deviation of 0.109 compared to 0.126 for the prediction given by Scheperboer, et al. (4).

In response to the first objective of this paper, it is demonstrated that the straightforward formulation determined by Scheperboer, et al. (4) is of good accuracy for a wider range of perforations arrangement than indicated in their paper and is less computationally demanding than FE procedure. The accuracy and standard deviation of the MEP is very similar in most of the domain explored. Yet, despite some improvement in the predictions for plates for the cases identified, there is insufficient benefit compared to Scheperboer, et al. (4).

However, it is encouraging that a basic uniform approximation to the force redistribution function can enable such accurate predictions to the elastic buckling capacity. It is expected that as this function approaches the true nature of the inhomogeneous force flow, the accuracy of the MEP will be improved, albeit at the compromise of increased computational demand. Furthermore, the combination of parameters that determine which buckling manifestation will dominate remain to be determined (*Fig. 1*). Given this information, the MEP may be further improved when a more accurate approximation to the deflection modeshape is chosen.

1. **Timoshenko, S. and Woinowsky-Krieger, S.** *Theory of Plates and Shells*. Second Edition. New York : McGraw-Hill, 1959.
2. **Navier, C.L.M.H.** Paris : Bull. Soc. Philomath, 1823. 75.
3. **Timoshenko, Stephen and Gere, James.** *Theory of Elastic Stability*. Singapore : McGraw-Hill Book Company, 1963, Second Edition.
4. *Local buckling of aluminium and steel plates with multiple holes.* **Scheperboer, Irene, Efthymiou, Evangelos and Maljaars, Johan.** 99, *Thin-Walled Structures* : 132-141, 2016, Vol. 2016.
5. *Elasto-plastic buckling of perforated plates under uniaxial compression.* **El-Sawy, Khaled M, Nazmy, Aly S and Martini, Mohammad Ikbal.** 42, 2004, *Thin-Walled Structures*, Vol. 2004, pp. 1083-1101.
6. *Elastic local buckling of perforated webs of steel cellular beam-column elements.* **Sweedan, Amr M.I. and El-Sawy, Khaled M.** 67, 1 February 2011, *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, Vol. 2011, pp. 1115-1127.
7. *Elastic stability of plates with circular and rectangular holes subjected to axial compression and bending moment.* **Maiorana, E, Pellegrino, C and Modena, C.** 47, 2009, *Thin-Walled Structures*, Vol. 2009, pp. 241-255.
8. *Elastic Buckling of Plates with Eccentrically Positioned Rectangular Perforations.* **Shakerley, T M and Brown, C J.** 1996, 1996, *Int. J. Mech. Sci*, Vol. 38, pp. 825-838.
9. *Elastic buckling of rectangular plates under linearly varying in-plane normal load with a circular cutout.* **Komur, M Aydin and Sonmez, Mustafa.** 35, 2008, *Mechanics Research Communications*, Vol. 2008, pp. 361-371.
10. *Numerical Evaluation of the Effect of Type and Shape of Perforations on the Buckling of Thin Steel Plates by Means of the Constructal Design Method.* **Lorenzini, G, et al.** 2016, 2016, *International Journal of Heat and Technology*, Vol. 34, pp. S9-S20.

11. *Stiffness and critical buckling load of perforated sheeting*. **Kathage, K, Misiak, Th and Saal, H.** 44, 2006, Thin-Walled Structures, Vol. 2006, pp. 1223-1230.
12. *Design formula for axially compressed perforated plates*. **Shanmugam, N.E., Thevendran, V and Tan, Y.H.** 34, 1999, Thin-Walled Structures, Vol. 1999, pp. 1-20.
13. *Experimental Study and Effective Width Method for Cold-Formed Steel Lipped Channel Stud Columns with Holes*. **Guo, Yanli and Yao, Xingyou.** 2021, Advances in Civil Engineering, Vol. 2021.
14. *Buckling Behaviour and Effective Width Design Method for Thin Plates with Holes under Stress Gradient*. **Guo, Yanil and Yao, Xingyou.** 2021, Mathematical Problems in Engineering, Vol. 2021.
15. *The Compressional Behaviour of Perforated Elemnets*. **Rhodes, J and Schneider, F D.** 1994. 12th International Speciality Conference on Cold-Formed Steel Structures. 6.
16. *The Design of Perforated Cold-Formed Steel Sections Subject to Axial Load and Bending*. **Davies, J, Leach, P and Taylor, A.** 29, 1997, Thin-Walled Structures, Vol. 1997, pp. 141-157.
17. **Ketsi, J.** *Local And Distortional Buckling of Perforated Steel Wall Studs*. Helsinki University of Technology : Dissertaion for the degree of Doctor of Science in Technology, 2000.
18. **AISI S100-16.** *North American Specification for the Design of Cold-Formed Steel Structural Members*. Washington DC, USA : American Iron and Steel Institute, 2016.
19. **BS EN 1993-1-3:2006.** *Eurocode 3. Design of steel structures - General rules - Supplementary rules for cold-formed members and sheeting*. London, UK : BSI, 2006.
20. **GB50017-2002.** *Technical Code for Cold-Formed Thin-Walled Steel Structures*. Beijing, China : Chinese National Standard, 2002.
21. *Elastic Buckling of thin plates with holes in compression or bending*. **Moen, C D and Schafer, B W.** 2009, Thin-Walled Structures, Vol. 47, pp. 1597-1607.
22. **Bazant, Zdenek P and Cedolin, Luigi.** *Stability of Structures*. London : World Scientific Publishing Co., 2010.
23. *Mathematic Identification of Influential Parameters on the Elastic Buckling of Variable Geometry Plate*. **Djelosevic, Mirko, et al.** 2013, Scientific World Journal, Vol. 2013.
24. *Increase in buckling loads of plates by introduction of cutouts*. **Gracia, Jorge Blesa and Rammerstorfer, Franz G.** 2019, 2019, Acta Mech, Vol. 239, pp. 2873-2889.
25. *Finite strip elastic buckling solutions for thin-walled metal columns with perforation patterns*. **Smith, Frank and Moen, Christopher D.** 79, 2014, Thin-Walled Structures, Vol. 2014, pp. 187-201.
26. **ABAQUS.** 11.2 Linear Perturbation analysis. *ABAQUS Version 6.6 Documentation*. [Online] ABAQUS, January 2009. [Cited: 15 December 2023].
27. *Buckling Behaviour and Post-Buckling Strength of Perforated Stiffened Compression Elements*. **Yu, Wei-Wen and Davies, C S.** Missouri, USA : s.n., 1971. International Speciality Conference on Colf-Formed Steel Structures. 5.
28. *Ultimate Capacity of Uniaxially Compressed Perforated Plates*. **Narayanan, R and Chow, F Y.** 2, 1984, Thin-Walled Structures, Vol. 1984, pp. 241-264.
29. *Direct Strength Design of Cold-Formed Steel Members with Perforations*. **Moen, C.D.** 2008, Dissertation (Ph.D), Vols. Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, Maryland.
30. **python.** random - Generate pseudo-random numbers. *python library*. [Online] python, 27 December 2023. [Cited: 27 December 2023].